

Exploiting Core Openness as Native-AI Enabler for Optimised UAV Flight Path Selection

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Abstract—Given that the use of the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) has been increased significantly the last years, it is deemed necessary to adopt innovative technologies and features, with a focus on automating drones' missions so as to revolutionize the way vertical industries operate. This automation can be achieved by the integration of UAVs in the cellular networks however, operational challenges such as signal quality variation of the network need to be addressed. In this regard, the paper discusses the potential for optimizing the automated UAV flights over the cellular networks. The optimization is focusing on an approach based on 3GPP Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and the openness of the core network for predicting the Quality of Service (QoS). Through the prediction of the QoS, the optimization of the flight path for UAVs in 5G and B5G networks is proposed and validated on top of an emulation tool that can support scenarios with UAVs.

Keywords—UAVs; QoS; NWDAF; B5G; APIs;

I. INTRODUCTION

A wide range of sectors could undergo a total transformation as a result of the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) usage in various use-cases and vertical industries. UAVs may send huge amounts of data in real-time, opening up a number of applications including remote sensing, precision farming, and disaster response. The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in UAVs facilitates the collecting and processing of data from many sensors, enabling more accurate and efficient decision-making. Moreover, automating drone missions could revolutionize the way vertical industries operate, resulting in significant productivity gains and time savings. This entails arranging infrequent drone missions or routine flights automatically, launching drones from vertiports without human assistance, gathering data in real time and utilizing artificial intelligence algorithms to analyze it, and making decisions. However, this opportunity for automated UAV missions is currently limited due to the lack of integration of UAVs in the business and operational processes of the various sectors.

The current restricted coverage range of technologies usually establish a direct link between the pilot and the UAV, in addition to the requirement of having a human pilot in the immediate area of the drone, minimizes further the potential business opportunity of automated flights. On the other hand, authorizing automated Beyond Visual Line of Sight (BVLoS) would allow a UAV to be operated remotely from a control center. In the light of the above, mission automation and BVLoS flights necessitate an end-to-end connectivity solution based on network infrastructure. This link connects the UAV to the user's facilities, as well as the UAV to its control center responsible for the automated mission. Towards this automated UAV missions, the most promising enabling technology is 5G and beyond cellular networks, which due to their performance characteristics are able to unlock the full potential of UAVs in many areas. As a result, cellular network operators and UAV-related sectors are thought to benefit from the integration of UAVs into cellular networks, which not only opens up a ton of new business potential but also improves the communication performance of three-dimensional (3D) wireless networks in the forthcoming 6G Networks.

Recent proof-of-concept trials [1] have proved the feasibility of transferring the control and communication channel of UAVs over 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) networks, maintaining the same piloting requirements as in the case of direct Command and Control (C2) links and even enhancing the capabilities of the UAV by offloading demanding processing tasks at the edge of the network [2]. On the other hand, large scale experiments have identified some operational challenges in the automated 5G-enabled UAV missions, which are related to 5G signal quality variation, when the UAV is airborne and is moving from one 5G cell to another (i.e., performing multiple handovers) [3]. An explanation for this is the fact that 5G and B5G networks are primarily intended for terrestrial use, with antennas angled downward towards the earth. Some theoretical, simulation-based research have

predicted an extremely fragile link in the air based on this rationale [4]. This means that a UAV may be covered by the side lobes of an antenna rather than the main lobe, or it could be connected to very distant base stations, since a UAV in the air is no longer affected by attenuation resulting from trees or buildings. The aforementioned situation that a 5G-enabled flying UAV experiences, affects the reliability of controlling and piloting the latter over the 5G network, since it results in i) low Quality of Service (QoS) of the 5G signal reception, which in turn may cause increased latency, reduced throughput and potentially packet losses between the UAV and the control station; ii) a significant increase in the number of handovers throughout the UAV flight. With the aim of fostering an efficient integration between the UAVs and the mobile operators, this paper proposes the use of a Native-Artificial Intelligence (AI) approach within the framework of 6G Networks. This approach relies on the utilisation of data obtained from the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) of the core network in order to feed an AI-module that in turn aids and optimizes the control decisions of a UAV. This set of data will ensure the proper prediction of the optimal way point path during a flight and therefore guaranteeing the best possible QoS. The optimal waypoint path will enable the mitigation of potential service interruption, which may be caused due to unexpected QoS downgrades or signal quality variations in the network due to multiple handovers.

Following this introductory section, the rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II initially introduces the 6G networks' vision and its relation to the UAVs' vertical industry. It also delves into the AI-native nature of the 6G networks. In Section III the distributed network approach is introduced, which is the framework for applying the proposed QoS prediction and optimization of the flight. Then in Section IV the proposed AI-enabled method is described along with its validation method, based on an tool capable of emulating UAV scenarios, among other capabilities. Finally, Section V concludes the paper, summarizing the current findings and the future work.

II. VISION OF THE 6G NETWORKS

A. 3GPP and UAVs

3GPP Working Groups (WGs) have been actively engaged in creating a mapping of the 6G system and establishing the connectivity requirements of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) to such networks in order to meet the needs of the rapidly expanding UAV sector. Towards this direction, 3GPP has investigated various scenarios and enabling technologies for integrating non-terrestrial components into new radio (NR). These studies propose several use cases for each of the three known usage scenarios enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), massive machine type communication (mMTC) and ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC). Release 17 which is the latest in a series of communications standards developed by the 3GPP, builds upon and remains compatible with the previous releases. To better serve UAV applications, the particular release specifies the mobile cellular capabilities that address UAVs' use cases. However, the specifications were designed in such a way that they can support UAV requirements without needing to be heavily changed for local

regulations. This was achieved by separating the aviation characteristics from the technical 3GPP details.

One of the main topics described in Rel.17, is the capability of the 3GPP system to enable the UAS components towards the establishment of the necessary connectivity between each other and UAV Traffic Management (UTM) for both line-of-sight and non-line-of-sight scenarios. In view of the foregoing, two separate interfaces that could be used to link 3GPP systems and UAV-related applications have been outlined. The first interface, which is described in TS 23.256 [5], allows for direct access to the 3GPP network features needed for UAV applications through its Network Exposure Function (NEF) interface. This is the most suitable interface for services such as UTM and UTM Service Providers (USS) that have a connection to the 3GPP system. TS 23.255 [6] refers to the second interface as the "higher level" interface due to its more abstract level of access to 3GPP network features. This higher-level interface provides a more generic application-layer approach with no integration with 3GPP system functions. Moreover, the report focuses on the development of building blocks for UAVs' applications and the detection and reporting of unauthorized UAVs to the UTM.

On the other hand, Release 18, which is a large leap forward in the 5G System (5GS) and for that reason 3GPP has determined to brand it as the first release of 5G Advanced, includes several updates related to UAVs. This release will introduce a variety of new technologies and features, including improved radio access capabilities, enhanced data rates, and expanded coverage. One of the most significant aspects related to UAVs, will be the ability to support the use of unlicensed spectrum. This opens up the possibility for UAVs to access the same level of performance as cellular networks, but without the need for a dedicated network infrastructure. This could enable the development of new services, such as low-latency communications for autonomous UAVs, or high-speed data transfer for applications such as drone-based surveillance. 3GPP Release 18 will also provide details on 5G NR support for devices on board aerial vehicles. Previously, 3GPP Release 15 enabled 4G LTE support for UAVs, which included more precise measurements, the reporting of the UAV's altitude, location, speed, and path, and the signaling to support subscription-based UAV identification. Similar features will be incorporated into 5G NR specifications targeting the improvement of broadcasting UAV identification and signaling to demonstrate UAV beamforming capabilities.

B. Native AI in 6G Networks

The forthcoming 6G network is anticipated to facilitate a stronger fusion of communication (networking) and computing aspects and AI will be treated as the cornerstone. In this sense, the evolution of telecom infrastructures towards 6G will involve the extensive use of AI, shifting the intelligence away from a centralized cloud towards the edge. This will be achieved through the use of highly integrated Information and Communication Technology (ICT) systems with computing and storage capabilities deployed at the edge, thus shaping the concept of "pervasive intelligence" and "native" AI. From an architectural standpoint, operating distributed AI at the edge might offer the best performance while also addressing individual and corporate data ownership concerns and adhering

to local and federal regulatory requirements. To enable these features, 6G networks must include all the necessary features, such as algorithms, neural networks, databases, and APIs, that are crucial for its implementation. Networked AI, which differs from the current “Cloud AI,” will also be a part of the 6G network aiming to provide native AI capabilities. These Native AI capabilities will be built into 6G networks from the ground up, and distributed machine learning in particular will be supported by the network architecture. Simply said, 6G is a network that will support and enhance AI capabilities in the sense that numerous network components will carry out AI and machine learning tasks. For example, the cloud-based data centers in use today will evolve into native AI-neural centers. This necessitates for a more distributed architecture with embedded mobile edge computing capabilities to combine local data collection, training, reasoning-inference for improved privacy and decreased latency/bandwidth consumption.

The distributed native-AI in 6G networks can prove to be of significant importance in improving the airborne waypoint trajectory for autonomous flying drones used for sensing purposes. More specifically, these autonomously flying UAVS, controlled with C2-delivered over the cellular channel, are of significant importance, as discussed in the previous section of this paper. They are designed to operate under regions with high QoS signal quality and coverage; otherwise, poor quality may result in unreliable flying status and finally crash of the drone. Building upon this feature, the following section of this paper proposes an AI-native approach for optimizing the waypoint trajectory of the UAV within the context of 6G Networks. This approach involves providing the ground control station with predictions on the QoS level of each cell operating along the mission path that the UAV is set to fly.

III. PROPOSED NATIVE-AI APPROACH FOR UAV TRAJECTORY OPTIMIZATION

A. Distributed architectural approach for QoS prediction

In principle, the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) is a functional component responsible for collecting and analyzing network data so as to provide valuable insights and support decision-making processes. The NWDAF operates by interacting with various entities and facilitates the centralized collection and analysis of data. This is achieved through event subscriptions from entities such as Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF), Policy Control Function (PCF), Unified Data Management (UDM), Network Slice Access Control Function (NSACF), Application Function (AF), either directly or via NEF. The NWDAF also gathers information about Network Functions (NFs). When specific analytics can be performed independently by a 5G Core NF, a dedicated NWDAF can be co-located within that NF. In such cases, the data used by the NF for analytics must be accessible to enable centralized deployment of the NWDAF. 5GS NFs and Operations Administration and Maintenance (OAM) framework decides then on how to use the data analytics supplied by NWDAF so as to improve the performance of the network, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Moreover, NWDAF employs existing service-based interfaces to communicate with other 5G NFs and OAM. As an outcome a NF can make the data analytics available to any consumer NF via a service-based interface.

Fig. 1. NWDAF as network data analytics function in the 5G system

Release 17 has placed significant emphasis on enhancing the capabilities of the NWDAF. These enhancements include decomposing the NWDAF logic into two distinct components namely the Model Training Logical Function (MTLF) and the Analytics Logical Function (ANLF), as depicted in Fig. 2. Additionally, Rel. 17 introduced support for utilizing UE’s data as input for data analytics, facilitated through the application server [8]. Specifically, the characteristics of the logical functions within NWDAF are as follows:

- Analytics logical function (ANLF) which is a logical function in NWDAF, which performs inference, derives analytics information (i.e., derives statistics and/or predictions based on Analytics Consumer request) and exposes analytics service
- Model Training logical function (MTLF) which is a logical function in NWDAF, which trains Machine Learning (ML) models and exposes new training services (e.g., providing trained ML model).

In the case that NWDAF is used as an AI-enabler for the network, multiple NWDAFs can be set up in a Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN). One of these NWDAFs can act as an aggregate point collecting analytics data from the other NWDAFs (which may be covering different service areas). The aggregate NWDAF then utilizes the collected data to generate aggregated analytics or to independently create its own analytics. This setup allows for efficient data consolidation and analysis, enabling comprehensive insights and AI-driven decision-making processes in the context of 6G networks. The latter is the case of the proposed Native-AI framework for UAVs, which considers a distributed architectural approach, where multiple instances of the NWDAF are utilized for feeding analytics information to the aggregator NWDAF, in which a MTLF trains ML models and exposes new training services (e.g., providing trained ML model) specifically for the UAV industry. Thus, the provided analytics information stemming from the aggregator NWDAF are not only statistical information of the past events, but based on the proposed model, the NWDAF provides predictive information derived from the ML model of the embedded logical function.

B. Proposed approach for UAV trajectory optimization based on core openness

As stated previously, QoS is a key factor that determines the success of UAV applications. Sudden QoS degradation can

cause latency, packet loss, and jitter, which can disrupt the UAV's navigation and control systems, leading to unexpected results. Furthermore, poor QoS can cause unreliable communication between the UAV and the ground station, which can lead to data loss and decreased safety. Therefore, ensuring high QoS is critical for applications related to UAVs. 5G communication systems support in advance notifications on potential QoS change on applications directly through the NWDAF or NEF whether they belong to the MNO's trust domain or not, respectively [7]. Based on the predicted QoS changes, the application can adjust and take the necessary actions (e.g., change the fully automated flight-plan to remote assisted) to ensure the best possible QoS and prevent the session from being terminated. In the light of the above, the proposed approach for UAV trajectory optimization relies on the MTLF components of the Aggregator NWDAF, which gather information from all the relevant data producers within the UAV ecosystem, namely the 5G Core and the RAN, as well as the UAV application server, which is tightly integrated to the NEF as depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The proposed approach for exploiting NWDAF as technology enabler for Native-AI Predictions

Therefore, given that the mission of a UAV is planned with a specific launch and landing site, without optimizing the flight plan facilitated by the MTLF through the NWDAF at the service level of each cell the UAV traverses, the most straightforward path would be a direct line from takeoff to the landing site. This flight path ignores the fact that the UAV will fly via a cell with a degraded QoS as depicted in red color in Fig. 3, which may result in loss of control and therefore potential crash of the drone.

Fig. 3. The two alternative flight paths of a UAV to fly from Cell (1,1) to Cell (1, n) based on QoS levels of each cell

In the proposed approach, the UAV controller prior to the initiation of the mission, will receive inputs from the NWDAF. These inputs are based on the data received from the Core, the RAN, the NEF, as well as the UAV controller itself (i.e., the takeoff and landing locations). By modelling the received data and applying a native-AI prediction algorithm, an optimized flight path between the take-off and the landing locations will be provided to the UAV controller, considering the QoS provisions of the various cells through which the UAV should fly in order to ensure the safe and secure navigation from its take-off location to its designated landing site. Observing the cell topology that is provided in Fig. 3, where the UAV plans to fly from cell (1,1) to cell (1,5), it becomes apparent that the specific direct path goes through cells with not-guaranteed QoS (grey cells) or even degraded QoS (red cell). However, an alternate path is available via cells (2,2), (3,3) and (2,4), which offer a guaranteed QoS to the UAV. Selecting this alternate path ensures that the flight control remains unaffected and mitigates the risk of performance deterioration.

IV. VALIDATION OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

For the experimental validation of the proposed method an emulated testbed was utilised. This testbed is capable of defining specific cell topologies, UAV trajectories, and exposing 3GPP standardized APIs that provide relevant data [9] in order for an AI-model to be properly trained. This setup allowed for the proper training of the AI model by exposing it to the necessary information required for accurate analysis and decision-making. As a means to validate and demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in the simulated environment, the simplified yet realistic paradigm of the different paths and UEs through different cells was implemented in the emulator tool, as depicted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The emulated scenario at the GUI of the emulator

The data generated within the emulator based on the configured scenario, primarily pertains to the active subscriptions of the UEs, enabling the monitoring of congestion within each cell. It also includes characteristics derived from the AsSessionwithQoS API and the QoS flows that correspond to a list of standardized 5QI values [10], which in turn define a set of QoS characteristics. As a result, the

UAV application server can retrieve relevant information by invoking the `/api/v1/qosInfo/qosCharacteristics` that has been implemented in the emulator. Subsequently the data that were produced from the 3GPP standardized API, was used in order to train a simple AI-model (e.g., linear regression) and test the validity of the proposed framework. Upon performing the experiment in the emulated environment without and with feeding the UAV Application server with the predicted path optimization, the results have shown that the reliability and the trust of the UAV flight can be significantly improved by using the openness of the core network as an enabler for realizing native-AI functions for specific vertical applications.

Fig. 5. Validation Results of the proposed approach

As depicted in Fig. 5, it is evident that when the UAV operates without coupling the UAV controller with the native-AI function (i.e., simple flight), the achieved QoS levels fall significantly short in comparison to the scenario where the predicted flight plan is utilized (i.e., AI-enabled flight). More specifically, we observe that even if both UAV flights start with a moderate degree (2-3) of QoS at Cell-1 and Cell 5, respectively, these cells do not guarantee a constant QoS and are shared among the two paths meaning that significant variations can happen during the remainder of the flight since the takeoff and landing spots are within their coverage areas. In the context of the AI-enabled flight, the emulation tool estimates that the UAV will experience consistently high levels of Quality of Service (QoS) across Cells 2, 3, and 4 within the selected path. This indicates a highly reliable UAV control over the mobile network. On the other hand, in the case of a simple flight, the QoS levels experienced by the UAV are mainly moderate (on a scale ranging the QoS level from 1 to 6), and significant degradation is observed as the UAV traverses Cell-3 along the simple flight path. This degradation in QoS poses a risk of control loss and potential mission abort for the UAV.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the utilization of native AI capabilities and the openness of the core network for the prediction and optimization of UAV flight paths in 5G and B5G networks, while taking into consideration the QoS characteristics, has been presented. The proposed method has been thoroughly tested and validated within an emulated environment that offers precise cell topologies, UAV trajectories, and access to 3GPP standardized APIs,

providing valuable data for experimentation. The validation confirms the applicability of the approach and its effectiveness in generating accurate and reliable results. The findings after the validation process underscore the significant potential of leveraging core openness as an enabler for delivering native AI functionalities to a wide range of vertical applications. The openness of the core network is shown to be a valuable and reliable data source for training predictive models, which in turn enable accurate and effective optimization for UAV flight paths. Moreover, the utilization of a distributed NWDAF proves to be an effective approach for collecting data from various system components. This approach enhances the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the predictive models, leading to more robust and reliable results. To further enhance the research, future work will focus on incorporating time series analysis and conducting a comparative analysis of various AI models and sophisticated approaches (e.g., decision trees, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)), to forecast the load of the network. This analysis would contribute to optimizing the flight paths of UAVs by leveraging the predictions obtained from these models. Additionally, there is room to explore other features of the NWDAF expanding the scope of the research.

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